

Tahar Haddad's Feminist Thought: Between Tradition and Modernity

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Abstract: Often regarded as the father of Tunisian feminist thought, Tahar Haddad was a Muslim reformer during the French protectorate in Tunisia. His most famous work, *Imra'atu-nā fī-l-sharī'a wa-l-mujtama'*, published in 1930, encompasses most of his thoughts on gender roles and greatly impacted his society, to the point that it is rumored to have been one of the sources of inspiration for the drafting of the Tunisian Law of Personal Status (1956). The book was the first of its kind to express the need for inheritance rights to be the same regardless of the receiver's gender, as well as one of the first ones to push for the abolition of polygyny and repudiation. It was also notable for stating the importance of national education, including physical education, and rallying to make it extensible to female students. As such, Haddad received much criticism, particularly from conservatives who thought he had deviated from the Islamic law, despite the book making continuous references to the Qur'an and Sunna. As much as it was a revolutionary work, some of the author's points of view still perpetuate certain gender stereotypes and norms regarding women. This paper aims to revisit the book, pointing out its key elements in the fight for gender equality as well as its strengths and weaknesses.

Keywords: Tahar Haddad, Colonial Tunisia, Feminism in the Arab World, Islamic law, Islamic Reformism

I. Introduction

In 1930, in the middle of the nationalist struggle for independence, the publishing of a certain book shook the Tunisian society. Its aim was to drastically change the role of women in all aspects of life, both private and public, and empower them to become a leading motor for the nation. Despite its Islamic rooting, the thought the book encompassed was perceived as ground-breaking, revolutionary and even heretic. The author himself was chastised by society and prosecuted by *shuyūkh* of the Zaytūna mosque, who deemed him a traitor to Islam. Shortly after being published, the book was declared illegal and a number of other works trying to demonstrate the wrong in its ideas flooded the market. A handful of *'ulamā'* issued pamphlets condemning the book and the majority of journals of Tunisia were more often than not full of articles either attacking or defending the author. The nationalist leaders did not shy away from criticizing it either, almost all of them insisting in the need of maintaining traditions in order to differentiate the Tunisian character and identity from that of the European oppressor. However, was the book really that disruptive towards the traditional gender roles in the country?

Imra'atu-nā fī-l-sharī'a wa-l-mujtama' (*Our Women in the Islamic law and Society*), was written by Tahar Haddad¹ (1899–1935), a Zaytūna graduate, and was the epitome of his activism

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¹ The appropriate transcription for his name should be al-Tāhir al-Haddād. However, we will be using the most common form of his name, as he is most often referred to as "Tahar Haddad" in European languages.